

IMPROVING VOCABULARY SKILLS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Vohidova Matluba Ma'rufbekovna

Namangan viloyati To'raqo'rg'on tumani 54- sonli

maktab ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7079561>

Abstract: this article illustrates the types of vocabulary, how the teacher teaches it and ways of the learning it. This article helps new teachers and students.

Abstract: bu maqola lug'at boyligi turlari, uni o'rgatish usullari va yo'llari haqida o'qituvchilarga ma'lumot beradi.

Introduction: A vocabulary is a set of familiar words within a person's language. A vocabulary, usually developed with age, serves as a useful and fundamental tool for communication and acquiring knowledge. Acquiring an extensive vocabulary is one of the largest challenges in learning a second language.

Vocabulary growth

During its infancy, a child instinctively builds a vocabulary. Infants imitate words that they hear and then associate those words with objects and actions. This is the listening vocabulary. The speaking vocabulary follows, as a child's thoughts become more reliant on their ability to self-express without relying on gestures or babbling. Once the reading and writing vocabularies start to develop, through questions and education, the child starts to discover the anomalies and irregularities of language. In first grade, a child who can read learns about twice as many words as one who cannot. Generally, this gap does not narrow later. This results in a wide range of vocabulary by age five or six, when an English-speaking child will have learned about 1500 words.

Vocabulary grows throughout one's life. Between the ages of 20 and 60, people learn about 6,000 more lemmas, or one every other day. An average 20-year-old knows 42,000 lemmas coming from 11,100 word families. People expand their vocabularies by for e.g. reading, playing word games, and participating in vocabulary-related programs. Exposure to traditional print media teaches correct spelling and vocabulary, while exposure to text messaging leads to more relaxed word acceptability constraints.

One of the easiest ways to bolster your existing writing skills is to add new words to your written vocabulary. The English language is among the most voluminous of all languages, and this means that you'll never run out of vocabulary words to learn and use. All forms of the written word—from fiction to journalism to essay writing to poetry—benefit from a strong vocabulary. To that end, the time you spend improving your vocabulary skills is actually time invested in your writing skills.

Ways to Improve Your Vocabulary

Most of us have not spent much time learning new vocabulary since we were high school or college students. Thankfully you can always pick up where you left off. Here are some tips to help you start learning new vocabulary words:

1. Develop a reading habit. Vocabulary building is easiest when you encounter words in context. Seeing words appear in a novel or a newspaper article can be far more helpful than seeing them appear on vocabulary lists. Not only do you gain exposure to unfamiliar words; you also see how they're used.

2. Use the dictionary and thesaurus.

Online dictionaries and thesauruses are helpful resources if used properly. They can jog your memory about synonyms that would actually be better words in the context of what you're writing. A full dictionary definition can also educate you about antonyms, root words, and related words, which is another way to learn vocabulary.

3. Play word games.

Classic games like Scrabble and Boggle can function as a fun way to expand your English vocabulary. Crossword puzzles can as well. If you really want to be efficient, follow up rounds of these word games with a little note-taking. Keep a list of the different words you learned while playing the game, and then study that list from time to time.

4. Use flashcards. A quick way to build a large vocabulary is to study a number of words via flashcards. In today's digital age, a wide array of smartphone apps make flashcards convenient and easy to organize. Aiming for one new word a day is reasonable. You can always go for more, but it may not be reasonable to assimilate dozens of English words every single day.

6. Use mnemonics. A mnemonic device is a form of word association that helps you remember words' definitions and proper uses. For instance think of the word obsequious which means "attempting to win favor from influential people by flattery." Break down that word into components: "obse" is the beginning of "obsessed," "qui" sounds like the French word for "yes" (oui), and "us" is like the word "us." So you can think of that big word obsequious as "obsessed with saying yes to us"—which is kind of what it means!

7. Practice using new words in conversation. It's possible to amass a huge vocabulary without actually knowing how to use words. This means you have to take it upon yourself to put your personal dictionary into use. If you come across an interesting word in your reading, make a point of using it in conversation. By experimenting in low-stakes situations, you can practice the art of word choice

and, with a with a little bit of trial and error, hone in on the right word for a particular context.

Used literature:

1. "504 Absolutely Essential Words"
2. "NTC Vocabulary Builders"
3. "Word Power Made Easy"

